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given rather than the standard error. To check whether the recovered juveniles belonged to the *M. graminicola* species, juveniles coming from each of the 18 banana trees were inoculated in 18 pots planted with rice (UPLRi5). Five weeks later, roots of these pots were washed out from the soil and examined for galls: all 18 root systems were severely galled with "hooked" terminal gall, characteristic of infestation of this rice variety with *M. graminicola*. Thus, the developed nematodes were *M. graminicola* and the three banana cultivars were scored as highly susceptible.

The most common banana cultivars in the Philippines (Saba, Lakatan, and Latundan) are able to multiply and carry the rice root-knot nematode *M. graminicola* on their roots. Suckers of banana are often moved from one place to another in the Philippines. When banana trees are planted near rice fields, the distance between the banana trees and the first row of rice is usually less than 2 m. Considering the extension of the root systems of both plants, reciprocal contamination by nematodes between rice and banana appears possible. The dissemination of these pests in this way can be much faster

than natural dispersion of nematodes, which move by about 10 cm per year. This possible fast dissemination could result in low variability of this nematode species throughout the Philippines.

Some additional studies are needed. Our study demonstrated the presence of *M. graminicola* in the roots but not in the corm of the suckers. If a sucker is moved from one place to another, the remaining parts of the roots can carry the nematode if there is no paring of the corm after uprooting. Carefully cutting out all the roots at the corm level could avoid transmission if the corm is not infested. This last possibility could be investigated by inoculation with *M. graminicola* of nematode-free suckers coming from tissue culture. The contamination of corm tissues of inoculated suckers could be checked by histology. *Radopholus similis* infests the roots and the corm of banana (Gowen and Queneherve 1990). This explains why this nematode species was found in our inoculation experiment (see table) despite the paring of the corms. The treatment for *M. graminicola* would be the same as for *R. similis*: disinfect the corm by dipping in hot water or use nematode-free ba-

nana seedlings from tissue culture (Gowen and Queneherve 1990).

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Predation of freshwater fish on golden apple snail, *Pomacea canaliculata* Lam., under greenhouse conditions

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Fish are potential predators of snails (Slootweg et al 1994, Halwart 1994). However, studies on predation by freshwater fish on the golden apple snail (GAS) (*Pomacea canaliculata* Lam.) in rice fields are limited (Halwart 1994,

Cagauan 1999). At the PhilRice greenhouse, we investigated the predatory effect of four freshwater fish: *Oreochromis niloticus*, *Cyprinus carpio*, red-bellied pacu *Piaractus brachypomus*, and Asian catfish *Clarias macrocephalus* on

GAS. *O. niloticus* eats mostly plankton, *C. carpio* consumes detritus and benthic organisms, and *P. brachypomus* feeds on zooplankton, insects, snails, and decaying plants. These fish are exotic in the Philippines. *C. macrocephalus*, a

native of many Asian countries, is carnivorous. Currently, *O. niloticus*, *C. carpio*, and *C. macrocephalus* are cultured as food in many Asian countries, including the Philippines. *P. brachypomus*, a native of Brazil, was introduced to the Philippines from Singapore between 1980 and 1989 as an ornamental aquarium fish.

Two experiments used a high GAS density of 32 snails m⁻² with *O. niloticus* and *C. carpio*, whereas three used a low GAS density of 8 snails m⁻² with *C. carpio*, *P. brachypomus*, and *C. macrocephalus*. Each test run involved one fish species in three sizes, small (<10 g), medium (11–20 g), and large (21–30 g for *O. niloticus*, *C. carpio*, and *C. macrocephalus* and 30–50 g for *P. brachypomus*), with three densities (one, two, and three fish m⁻²). Fish were stocked 1 wk after rice transplanting and cultured for 3 wk. Initial and final individual length, weight, and mouth opening of the fish were measured. Thirty microplots (1 × 1 m) planted with 21-d-old rice seedlings (spacing: 25 × 25 cm) were infested with two sizes of GAS, <10-mm and 10–20-mm shell height, immediately after rice transplanting. In experiment 2, snails were color-coded by size. Half of the total GAS density plot⁻¹ consisted of small-sized GAS and the other half had large-sized GAS. Missing and damaged rice plants were recorded before fish stocking and harvest. GAS were counted and measured at the end of 4 wk. The main effects of the absence and presence of fish were analyzed by ANOVA in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Fish effect was further partitioned into effects of fish density, size, and their interaction. The least significant difference was used to compare means.

In Experiment 1 (high GAS density), the presence of *O. niloticus* and *C. carpio* significantly reduced GAS density after 3 wk by 52% and 35%, respectively. However, GAS densities of more than 10 m⁻² with the two fish species were not desirable as they could cause heavy damage to the rice plants. The effects of fish density, size, and their interaction were not significant.

In Experiment 2 (low GAS density), *C. carpio* significantly reduced the mean GAS density by 43%. *C. carpio* reduced <10-mm GAS density by 57%, whereas the decrease in large-sized GAS (10–20 mm) was not significant. Based on the regression analysis of fish mouth opening and body weight, that is, $Y = 4.394 + 0.174X$ (n = 68, R = 0.923, P < 0.001), a fish with an initial body weight of 5–40 g had a mouth opening of 5–12 mm. This range of mouth opening was not suitable to GAS with a shell height of >12 mm. For GAS with

10–20-mm shell height to be controlled, the body weight of the fish must be ≥30 g so that the corresponding mouth opening is ≥10 mm. Fish density, size, and their interaction did not contribute any significant variation to GAS density.

P. brachypomus significantly reduced the density of both sizes of GAS by about 63% (see table). The corresponding reductions in small and large GAS were 63% and 58%, respectively. Based on the relationship of mouth opening to body weight, that is, $Y = 7.607 + 0.132X$ (n = 170, R = 0.865, P < 0.001), fish used had an initial body weight of 5–62 g and a mouth opening of 8–15 mm. This range of mouth opening was suitable to GAS with shell heights of 4–16 mm. After 21 d, about 21% of the GAS had shell heights of 12–18 mm; 7% had 20–40 mm; 53%, 31–40 mm; and 19%, 40–48 mm. In the same period, fish body weight ranged from 6 to 68 g

Effect of freshwater fish on the density of golden apple snail (GAS), *Pomacea canaliculata*, compared with control rice microplots (no fish) at PhilRice screenhouse, Mar to Dec 2001.

Experiment	Treatment	Mean GAS density 21 d after fish stocking ^a (no. m ⁻²)		
High GAS density (32 snails m⁻²)				
	Without <i>O. niloticus</i>	28.7		
	With <i>O. niloticus</i>	13.9		
		P = <0.001**		
	Without <i>C. carpio</i>	27.0		
	With <i>C. carpio</i>	17.6		
		P = 0.040*		
Low GAS density (8 snails m⁻²)				
		GAS shell height (mm)		
		<10	10–20	Total
	Without <i>C. carpio</i>	3.7	3.3	7.0
	With <i>C. carpio</i>	1.6	2.5	4.1
		P = 0.023*	P = 0.227 ns	P = 0.011*
	Without <i>P. brachypomus</i>	3.0	3.7	6.7
	With <i>P. brachypomus</i>	1.1	1.6	2.7
		P = 0.004**	P = 0.0138	P = 0.005**
	Without <i>C. macrocephalus</i>	2.0	2.7	4.7
	With <i>C. macrocephalus</i>	2.3	2.5	4.8
		P = 0.666 ns	P = 0.840 ns	P = 0.902 ns

^aP = significance level. ** = significant at P < 0.01, * = significant at P < 0.05, ns = not significant.